

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF THE FERRIC THIOSULPHATE COMPLEX. PART III

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The extinction coefficient of the labile ferric thiosulphate complex at wave-length 500 m μ and the instability constant of the complex at ionic strength 0.12 have been determined. For the evaluation of the concentration of free S₂O₃²⁻ ion, it is necessary to take into consideration the various side equilibria. With more such equilibria, the uncertainty increases in the calculation of free S₂O₃²⁻ ion concentration. No foreign electrolyte has been used in our experiment, hence no new side equilibria except those inherent in the system are introduced. This has led to a more precise evaluation of the free S₂O₃²⁻ ion concentration. The values for the extinction coefficient (500) and for the instability constant (1.057 × 10⁻²) at 0.12 ionic strength of the complex are therefore reasonably accurate.

The coloured intermediate, FeS₂O₃⁺, produced by the reaction of thiosulphate with ferric salts, is labile and its decay curve is S-shaped (Patnaik and Mahapatra, *Curr. Sci.*, 1955, 24, 195). It has been observed by Schmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 148, 321) that both the forward and back reactions

are extremely rapid. Let $K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+}$ be the instability constant of the complex. Then

$$K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+} = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{3+}][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]}{[\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

If the initial concentrations of Fe³⁺ and S₂O₃²⁻ ions be a and b respectively and c , that of the intermediate FeS₂O₃⁺ at zero time, *i.e.*, just at the moment of mixing the solutions of thiosulphate and the ferric salt, equation (2) reduces to

$$K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+} = \frac{(a-c)(b-c)}{c} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

and since c is small, neglecting higher powers of c , we get

$$ab - c(a + b) = K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_3^+} \cdot c \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

According to Beer's law, the optical density D_{t_0} at zero time, *i.e.*, when the solutions are just mixed, becomes

$$D_{t_0} = \log \frac{I_0}{I \text{ at zero time}} = \epsilon \cdot c \cdot d$$

or
$$c = \frac{D_{t_0}}{\epsilon \cdot d} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where I_0 = intensity of the incident light; I at zero time = intensity of the transmitted light at zero time; d = the thickness of the liquid layer; ϵ = the extinction coefficient.

The value of I at zero time can be obtained as described previously (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 243). Substituting the value of c from equation (5) in equation (4) we get

$$ab - \frac{D_{10}}{\epsilon.d} (a + b) = K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_8^{2+}} \frac{D_{10}}{\epsilon.d}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{ab}{D_{10}} = \frac{a + b}{\epsilon.d} + \frac{K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_8^{2+}}}{\epsilon.d} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

On the right side of equation (6), the term $K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_8^{2+}} / \epsilon.d$ is constant. In the term $(a + b)/\epsilon.d$, the numerator varies with change of a and b , while $1/\epsilon.d$ remains constant. It is evident that a straight line would be obtained by the plot of ab/D_{10} against $(a + b)$, the slope of which is equal to $1/\epsilon.d$. Since d is known, ϵ can be calculated which, on substitution in equation (5), gives the value of c . With the help of equation (3), $K_{\text{FeS}_2\text{O}_8^{2+}}$ can also be evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of sodium thiosulphate in water and that of ferric perchlorate in perchloric acid were used. So the ions inherent in the system are Fe^{3+} , Na^+ , H^+ , ClO_4^- and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$. All side equilibria must involve these ions. The hydrogen-ion concentration was maintained at 0.05N. The concentrations of the thiosulphate and ferric perchlorate solutions were so chosen that the ionic strength was about 0.12. No new ions were introduced.

TABLE I
Log I of different composition ($R_1, \dots, R_7$) against time.

Time. ...	R_1	R_2	R_3	R_4	R_5	R_6	R_7
	A-10 B-7.5	A-10 B-5.0	A-7.5 B-10	A-7.5 B-7.5	A-7.5 B-5.0	A-5.0 B-10	A-5.0 B-7.5
5 sec.	0.699	1.079	0.699	0.916	1.230	1.000	1.176
10	0.778	1.114	0.778	0.977	1.261	1.070	1.211
15	0.903	1.176	0.903	1.061	1.301	1.154	1.273
20	1.041	1.255	1.041	1.161	1.363	1.249	1.342
25	1.204	1.357	1.150	1.284	1.427	1.347	1.419
30	1.352	1.454	1.322	1.394	1.495	1.447	1.505
35	1.505	1.562	1.447	1.505	1.569	1.535	1.574
40	1.613	1.648	1.544	1.594	1.636	1.607	1.638
45	1.703	1.728	1.636	1.672	1.699	1.672	1.697
50	1.778	1.796	1.695	1.763	1.754	1.720	1.740
55	1.831	1.851	1.746	1.780	1.799	1.761	1.778
60	1.872	1.893	1.784	1.818	1.836	1.792	1.808
65	1.902	1.924	1.813	1.848	1.866	1.823	1.834
70	1.927	1.942	1.838	1.870	1.882	1.840	1.853
75	1.943	1.964	1.857	1.892	1.914	1.850	1.869
80	1.957	1.973	1.875	1.907	1.929	1.869	1.884
85	1.966	1.982	1.889	1.919	1.945	1.885	1.896
90	1.974	1.986	1.900	1.929	1.946	1.895	1.906
95	1.979	1.987	1.909	1.939	1.964	1.904	1.914
100	1.981	1.915	1.915	1.945	1.911	1.911	1.920

A and B are given in m. moles per litre where A = Fe^{3+} , & B = $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$

The experimental details for determining the concentrations of free Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions have been described previously (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 459).

In Table I, the logarithms of the transmitted light for different composition $R_1, R_2, R_3, \dots$ of the reactants have been noted against time. A and B denote the actual concentrations (not the effective concentration) of ferric perchlorate and sodium thiosulphate in m. moles per litre. Wave-length used was $500 \text{ m}\mu$ and the working temperature was $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

TABLE II

[Calculated values of a, b and c are expressed in m. moles per litre].

Compositions.	R_1 .	R_2 .	R_3 .	R_4 .	R_5 .	R_6 .	R_7 .
$[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \times 10^3$ (a)	9.5	9.5	7.1	7.2	7.3	4.8	4.8
$[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] \times 10^3$ (b)	4.2	2.8	5.6	4.2	2.8	5.6	4.2
Log I at zero time	0.670	1.051	0.670	0.895	1.220	0.966	1.157
D_{10}	1.330	0.939	1.330	1.105	0.780	1.034	0.843
$\frac{ab}{D_{10}} \times 10^6$	30.03	28.36	29.90	27.36	25.76	25.99	23.91
$(a+b) \times 10^3$	13.70	12.30	12.70	11.40	10.00	10.40	9.00
$c \times 10^3$	1.77	1.25	1.77	1.47	1.04	1.38	1.12
$K_{\text{Fe}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3} \times 10^2$	1.061	1.023	1.153	1.064	1.042	1.046	1.012

Table II shows the calculated values of the concentrations of Fe^{3+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions in m. moles per litre after taking into consideration all side equilibria as described

FIG. 1

previously (*loc. cit.*). The values of I at zero time obtained by extrapolation have also been recorded. The value of $\log I_0$ for each case was 2 as 100% transmission

with the standard cell was always maintained. A straight line is obtained by the plot of ab/D_{t_0} against $(a+b)$. The slope of this line (Fig. 1) gives a value 1.333×10^{-3} for $1/\epsilon.d$. The thickness of the liquid layer was 1.5 cm, so the value of ϵ is 500. Since D_{t_0} for each of the compositions R_1 , R_2 , etc. are known, using the value of 500 for the extinction coefficient (ϵ), the value of c for each composition at zero time have been calculated from equation (5) and recorded in Table II. With the help of equation (3), the value of the instability constant has been calculated in each case. The average value of the constant of the complex for ionic strength 0.12 may be taken as 1.057×10^{-2} at 25°.

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